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Joint Reward Management Strategies and Their Influence on Teachers' Performance in Public Secondary Schools, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

Teacher performance is a multifaceted construct influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors. Research indicates that reward systems significantly impact employee effort, job satisfaction, and retention, which are crucial for organisational success. This study, however, investigated the influence of joint reward management strategies on teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. A correlational research design was adopted, guided by three research questions and corresponding hypotheses. The study population consisted of 7,254 teachers (3,642 males and 3,612 females) in 286 public senior secondary schools across the 23 local government areas of Rivers State. The sample size comprised 725 teachers selected from 29 schools, determined through a multistage sampling technique. Twenty-nine schools were chosen using simple random sampling through balloting, while the teachers were selected using a proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Two researcher-designed instruments were used for data collection. Both employed a four-point scale: Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1). Face validity was assessed by three experts (two from Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation at the University of Port Harcourt), confirming clarity and relevance. Reliability coefficients, computed via Cronbach's Alpha, were 0.86 (TPQ) and 0.85 (RMSQ). Data collection spanned two weeks, with 689 out of 725 questionnaires retrieved (95% return rate). Hypotheses were tested using t-test with simple regression, while the relationship strength was measured via the coefficient of determination ($R^2 \times 100\%$). Findings revealed that retirement benefit reward, recognition reward and reward management strategies relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. The study concluded that increased rewards for teachers lead to greater teaching productivity in these schools. It was recommended amongst others that public secondary school administrators in Rivers State should have retirement reward plans for all the teachers, which can be presented to them at the point of retirement.

Keywords: Reward Management Strategies, Teachers' Performance, Public Secondary Schools, Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

Reward is an important aspect of staff personnel management, and its effect on productivity is significant. It refers to the compensation given to an employee who contributes to the production of goods and services. However, compensation is not only a reward for services rendered to the organisation but also a source of recognition and livelihood for employees. It is directly related to their comfort and welfare.

Abraham and Nwabueze (2016) defined reward as the totality of financial and non-financial entitlements an employee receives in return for working in an organisation.

The reward system is an integration of the resources and course of actions that inform the selection of a mix of rewards aimed at facilitating the attraction and retention of employees, and to encourage employees' effort, cooperation as well as willingness to learn new skills and to adapt to change (Torrington et al 2009). In a simple word, Armstrong (2010) defined reward system as the interrelated processes and practices that combine to ensure that reward management is carried out effectively to the benefit of the organisation and the people who work there. This indicates that the reward strategy adapted by any organisation must align with the Human Resources and business strategies of the organisation.

Zigon (1998) defines rewards as something that increases the frequency of an employee's action. This definition highlights a key desired outcome of rewards and recognition: improved performance. Rewards beyond financial incentives can significantly boost motivation, building self-assurance and job fulfilment. Another key objective is improving staff retention, as ongoing recognition plays a vital role in keeping high-performing employees committed to the organisation.

To achieve these goals, reward systems should align closely with organisational strategies (Allen & Helms, 2002). For example, a company pursuing a product differentiation strategy might design reward practices to encourage innovation, ensuring unique products or services. Conversely, a company focused on cost reduction could emphasise rewards for cost-saving ideas and employee stock awards to sustain a cost-conscious culture.

Zigon (1998) suggests various methods to reinforce desired performance, increasing its recurrence and frequency compared to scenarios without such interventions. His approach offers managers flexibility in providing rewards at different cost levels while tailoring them to individual employee preferences. However, maximising effectiveness requires managers to invest time and effort in understanding employees' unique likes and dislikes.

How effective is non-cash recognition? Anecdotal evidence suggests that non-monetary recognition plays a significant role in retaining top talent and enhancing performance. A quick search of news databases reveals articles praising perks such as in-house chiropractors, spa gift certificates, extra days off, lavish parties, and personal trainers. Employers view these rewards as tools to retain high performers in a competitive job market—companies like Walt Disney World have documented the success of such recognition programs (Lynch, 2003).

Non-monetary rewards can be part of a comprehensive performance improvement strategy. It has been argued that non-monetary rewards are derived from the content of the work itself and include performance-oriented factors such as: interesting and challenging work, self-direction and responsibility, variety, creativity, opportunities to use one's skills and abilities, and sufficient feedback regarding the effectiveness of one's efforts (Hatice, 2012, cited in Ugwechi-Ishiaya, 2021).

Mohaney and Lederer (2006, cited in Ugwechi-Ishiaya, 2021) described intrinsic rewards as performance-related incentives such as praise from co-workers and supervisors, management recognition for well-performed job tasks, organisational status, personal satisfaction, and feelings of self-esteem. The type of recognition employees appreciate most is acknowledgement from those they work directly for. 78% of employees indicated that it was very or extremely important to be recognised by their managers for good work (Nelson, 2004). The most preferred form of recognition is sincere, timely praise with specific examples. Allen and Helms (2002) confirmed the importance of regular expressions of appreciation by managers and leaders in encouraging employee behaviours that align with strategic goals—a finding consistent across all the strategies they examined.

A reward system refers to the degree to which rewards are allocated based on employee performance rather than seniority, favouritism, or other non-performance criteria. Jacob (2005), citing Van der Post et al. (1997), noted that an organisation's reward system should reinforce the perception that most employees are good performers and should link rewards to performance. According to Mabaso and Dlamini (2017), for educational institutions to effectively impart knowledge to students, they must recruit and retain highly qualified teachers. However, this is nearly impossible without an effective reward policy

and a conducive work environment (Tahmeem & Sadia, 2018; Lestari, Syabarudin, Zurnali & Murad, 2018).

Okorie, Agabi, and Uche (2005) emphasised the need for teachers to adopt new approaches to teaching and learning. Relevant stakeholders should collaborate and pool their resources—whether intellectual, informational, persuasive, or financial—to address challenges such as implementing social distancing while maintaining connectedness. Teachers are more likely to embrace new teaching methods when they feel adequately rewarded and motivated. Uche and Amini-Phillips (2017) highlighted that teachers' core responsibilities include teaching, research, and community service. These activities, often conducted collaboratively daily, require full engagement from teachers—engagement that is best sustained through proper reward systems.

Statement of the Problem

Research indicates that teacher productivity in Rivers State's secondary schools is low, evidenced by poor lesson preparation, tardiness, inadequate classroom management, incomplete syllabus coverage, and biased assessments. This underperformance likely contributes to students' poor exam results, truancy, and off-task behaviour. A key factor may be ineffective reward management. Teachers face increased responsibilities without fair compensation, poor working conditions, and low morale, leading many to engage in petty trading or even soliciting bribes for grades. Consequently, teachers dedicate less time to instruction, further harming academic performance. Frequent strikes over funding and working conditions disrupt school calendars, worsening outcomes. Motivation and professional competence significantly influence teacher performance. When teachers trust that their efforts will be rewarded, productivity improves. However, school principals struggle to retain skilled staff, impacting institutional goals. Without addressing these issues, educational standards will decline, and schools risk losing productive teachers. This study explored the link between reward management strategies and teacher productivity in Rivers State's public secondary schools.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to investigate the influence of joint reward management strategies on teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

1. Determine the extent of relationship between retirement benefits reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Examine the extent of relationship between recognition reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. Ascertain the extent of relationship between joint reward management strategies (monetary, compensation, welfare, retirement and recognition) and teachers' productivity.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the extent of relationship between retirement benefits reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the extent of relationship between recognition reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. What is the extent of relationship between joint reward management strategies (monetary, compensation, welfare, retirement and recognition) and teachers' productivity?

Hypotheses

The understated null hypotheses were formulated to guide this study:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between retirement benefits reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between recognition reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between joint reward management strategies (monetary, compensation, welfare, retirement, and recognition) and teachers' productivity.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlational research design to examine the relationship between reward management strategies and teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The population comprised 7,254 teachers (3,642 male, 3,612 female) from 286 schools. A multistage sampling technique was used to select 725 teachers from 29 schools, randomly chosen via balloting, with teachers proportionally stratified. Data were collected using two researcher-designed instruments, titled Reward Management Strategies Questionnaire (RMSQ) and the Teachers’ Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ), both using a 4-point Likert scale (Very High to Very Low Extent). Face validity was assessed by three experts, and Cronbach’s Alpha confirmed reliability 0.86 and 0.85, respectively, for Reward Management Strategies Questionnaire (RMSQ) and Teachers’ Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ). The researcher, with the help of three assistants, administered 725 questionnaires face-to-face, retrieving 689 (95% return rate). Hypotheses were tested using t-test regression, while relationship strength was determined by coefficient of determination ($R^2 \times 100\%$), categorized as Very Low (0-25%), Low (26-50%), High (51-75%), or Very High Extent (76-100%).

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the extent of relationship between retirement benefits reward and teachers’ productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Retirement Benefits Reward and Teachers’ Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.993 ^a	.985	.985	Very High Extent

Data in Table 1 revealed that the regression and regression square coefficients are 0.993 and 0.985, respectively. The predictive power is determined by the coefficient of determinism. The coefficient of determinism of 98.5% reveals that retirement benefit reward relates to teachers’ productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

Research Question Two: *What is the extent of relationship between recognition reward and teachers’ productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Recognition Reward and Teachers’ Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.713 ^a	.508	.504	High Extent

Data in Table 2 revealed that the regression and regression square coefficients are 0.713 and 0.508, respectively. The predictive power is determined by the coefficient of determinism. The coefficient of determinism of 50.8% reveals that recognition reward relates to teachers’ productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question Three: *What is the extent of relationship between joint reward management strategies (monetary, compensation, welfare, retirement and recognition) and teachers’ productivity?*

Table 3: Multiple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Reward Management Strategies and Teachers’ Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.993 ^a	.987	.987	Very High Extent

Data in Table 4.6 revealed that the regression and regression square coefficients are 0.993 and 0.987 respectively. The predictive power is determined by the coefficient of determinism. The coefficient of determinism of 98.7% reveals that reward management strategies relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between retirement benefit reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Retirement Benefits Reward and Teachers' Productivity

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	.533	.158		3.376	.001
	retirement	.986	.005	.993	213.066	.000

Data in Table 4 reveals that the t-test value of 213.066 associated with simple regression is rejected because the significance value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, retirement benefit reward significantly relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between recognition reward and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test Associated with Simple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Recognition Reward and Teachers' Productivity

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	30.208	1.918		15.753	.000
	Recognition	.503	.053	.508	1.990	.000

Data in Table 5 reveals that the t-test value of 119.117 associated with simple regression is rejected because the significance value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, recognition reward significantly relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between joint reward management strategies (monetary, compensation, welfare, retirement, and recognition and teachers' productivity).

Table 6: ANOVA Associated with Multiple Regression of the Extent of Relationship between Reward Management Strategies and Teachers' Productivity

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12043.622	4	3010.905	12866.656	.000 ^b
	Residual	160.062	684	.234		
	Total	12203.684	688			

Data in Table 6 reveals that the ANOVA value F=12866.656 associated with multiple regression is rejected because the significance value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, reward management strategies significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Retirement benefit reward relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. Onyango (2014) also found that there is a positive correlation ($r=.181$) between employee benefits and organization performance. Finally, enhanced motivation can be attained when managers do their best to design the work setting so they become motivators in themselves while at the same time eliminating demotivating factors at the workplace. According to Berhan (2007), instructors were generally dissatisfied with extrinsic content of work such as salary, fringe benefits, incentives, job security, opportunity for training, and post-employment security. Hypothesis (1) revealed that retirement reward benefits significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

This finding revealed that recognition reward relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent. The finding of this is buttressed by Onyango (2014), who found that staff recognition is highly associated with staff performance. In the same vein, Nakabiri (2011) revealed that recognition of staff in training, involvement in decision making, and rotation of job positions relate to employees' job performance. The findings of this study are also in agreement with that of Turinawe (2011), who revealed that recognition of employees' commitment is a source of organisational performance. The hypothesis reveals that recognition reward significantly relates to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent. The hypothesis is supported by Kikoito (2014), who found that employees' recognition strategy is a significant predictor of employees' job productivity. This implies that recognition of teachers serves as a mainstream for them to discharge their task responsibilities expectedly in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

The findings of this study showed that reward management strategies relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent. This finding is in agreement with that of Nwokocha (2016), who opined that effective reward management strategies lead to employee performance, retention and productivity in the organisation. In the same vein, Moses (2016) found that the reward system has a positive impact on the performance of management and teachers. More so, Muogbo and Jacobs (2018) supported this finding in their report that reward management systems are determinants of employees' performance. The hypothesis reveals that reward management strategies significantly relate to teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent. The hypothesis is in tandem with the findings of Salah (2016), who found that there is a statistically significant relationship between reward management strategies and employees' job performance. The discussion of findings has shown that the proper conception and application of reward management strategies are essential in the achievement of effective teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings indicate that reward management strategies significantly enhance teacher productivity in Rivers State public secondary schools. Specifically, monetary rewards, compensation, welfare benefits, and retirement benefits have a very strong influence on productivity, while recognition rewards contribute to a high extent. This suggests that increased rewards for teachers lead to greater teaching productivity in these schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Public secondary school administrators in Rivers State should have retirement reward plans for all the teachers, which can be presented to them at the point of retirement.
2. The school administrators should always recognise and reward outstanding teachers who show a high level of productivity in their statutory functions.
3. The school authorities should be objective in their reward management strategies in order to enhance teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very high extent.

REFERENCES

- Abraham, N. M. & Nwabueze, A. I. (2017). Staff compensation and wage administration in schools. In W. A. Amaewhule, N. M. Abraham & J. D. Asodike (Eds.) *School Business Management: Theoretical & Practical Approach* (pp.214-234). Port Harcourt: Pearl Publishers International Limited.
- Torrington, D., Hall, L., & Taylor, S. (2006). *Human resource management* (6th ed). Harlow, Essex, U.K.: Prentice-Hall.
- Armstrong, M. (2010). *Armstrong's Essential Human Resource Management Practice: A Guide to People Management*. Kogan Page Limited
- Zigon, J. (1998). Team performance measurement. *The Journal for Quality and Participation*, 21(3), 48.
- Allen R. & Helms M. (2002). Employee perceptions of relationships between strategy rewards and organizational performance. *Journal of Business Strategies*, 19(2) 115-139.